

MONITORING THE DELAMINATION OF LAMINATED STRUCTURES BY USING CNT BUCKYPAPER

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ABSTRACT

Delamination is one of the main initial forms of damage in laminated structures. Monitoring and acquiring delamination stress of structures is of importance for structural design. Sensors based on nanomaterials have been attracting interest recently due to their piezoelectric effects. In this paper, carbon nanotube (CNT) buckypapers (BPs) are proposed to monitor the critical stress at initiation of delamination on both glass/epoxy and carbon/epoxy quasi-isotropic laminates. The laminates are designed to delaminate firstly under tensile load. Electrical resistance of laminates increases significantly with initiation of delamination. On one hand, slope of resistance-strain curve for the glass/epoxy laminate shows a sudden change when delamination occurs. Whereas resistance value for the carbon/epoxy laminate jumps obviously at the onset of delamination. The tests have exhibited that the CNT BPs have significant influence on the resistance change of laminates, showing potential to be used as a damage detector.

1 INTRODUCTION

Laminated structure is the mostly common construction form for advanced fiber reinforced polymer composites (FRPs). The relatively weak part always occurs in interlaminar region of laminates due to one by one stacking of unidirectional plies as well as no strengthening through the thickness of laminates [1]. Micro-cracks will present and orientate in the weakest direction of laminates when they are subjected to external load. Due to the presence of micro-cracks associated with edge effects, different plies tend to delaminate to prevent the stress transferring between plies [2]. Therefore, delamination is the major initial damage forms and which even leads to a sudden failure to laminates [1]. Practically, it is of importance to identify the moment at delamination initiation and avoid further propagation resulting in final failure [2]. Moreover, prediction of delamination initiation is also helpful to structure design.

Various sensors have been proposed to detect the initiation of delamination. But embedded sensors, such as fiber Bragg grating [3], piezoresistive sensors [4], and newly developed nano-sensors are studied and developed widely due to their real-time and in-situ characteristics. The former two sensors of above mentioned can solely provide sensitive function and have no contribution to the structural properties. Differently, nano-sensors cannot only serve as an embedded damage sensor but can also simultaneously provide structural contribution. Recently, one typical sensing approach consists of preparing a carbon nanotube (CNT) buckypaper (BP), made of CNTs only [5-15]. This embedded nano-sensor can be flexibly localized in a polymer or laminate at the site where it is needed for damage measurement [5, 7-13]. CNT BP is a macroscopic and paper-like nanomaterial composed of continuous entangled CNTs networks with a highly porous structure, in which, CNTs are free-standing in random directions. The individual CNTs within the BP are highly conductive, and

they form continuous conductive network. Once the integrity of the BP is destroyed, resistance variation of the bulk laminate can be self-recognized.

In the present study, porous CNT BPs are prepared and interleaved into both glass fiber/epoxy and carbon fiber/epoxy laminates. The inserted sites were the interfaces which tend to delaminate under in-plane tensile load. Effect of the CNT BPs on delamination initiation is experimentally investigated and simultaneously, resistance change of the studied laminates is detected by using a resistance instrument. If the resistance change of the laminates changed significantly at the same time, the CNT BPs thus could be directly used as an in-situ sensor. The initiation of delamination and corresponding stress level of the laminates are both obtained. Also, SEM observations are performed to demonstrate the occurrence of delamination.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

The CNT buckypapers (BPs) are directly used as laminate interleaves here. $[0^\circ/45^\circ/-45^\circ/90^\circ]_s$ quasi-isotropic laminates with and without CNT BPs, were prepared and investigated. For the laminate with CNT BPs, three CNT BPs were inserted into these interfaces, $-45^\circ/90^\circ$, $90^\circ/90^\circ$ (middle interface of laminate), and $90^\circ/-45^\circ$, in which the delamination tends to occur firstly under in-plane tension according to previous studies [16]. After stacking the plies into the intended laminates, they were put into a vacuum hot-press and the curing cycle was started, ramping from room temperature up to 130°C at a rate of $1^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ and was hold for 3 h at 130°C . The applied cure pressure was 0.7 MPa during the isothermal time. The final laminates were then cooled down to 60°C .

The test specimens were 250 mm by 25 mm in size according to ASTM D3039 standard. To form conductive path, two surfaces of the specimens within the gage length were firstly coated with conductive silver glue, then led copper wires to a Keithley 2450 voltage-current meter and monitored the electrical resistance during tensile testing. The tensile tests for both the base and reinforced laminate were conducted on a universal testing instrument (Model CSS-44020, Changchun Institute of Testing Machine, China), with a loading speed 2 mm/min. Five to eight specimens were tested for each laminate to evaluate the repeatability of the results. It should be noted that the in-plane resistance was examined for the glass fiber/epoxy laminate. On the contrary, the through-thickness resistance was considered for the carbon fiber/epoxy laminate.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig.1 describes the mechanical and electrical response of $[45/0/-45/\text{BP}/90/\text{BP}_{1/2}]_s$ glass/epoxy laminate. Due to the existence of 90 layers, transverse cracks would appear firstly in these layers with the increasing of load, and then these cracks propagate to the $90/90$ interface or $-45/90$ interfaces (see in Fig.2a), the weakest interfaces in this laminate. Thus, delamination initiates, which leads a sudden change to the slope of the $\Delta R/R_0$ %-strain curves (Fig.1, point A). Near this point, load drop is also observed, suggesting the delamination initiates. The delamination initiation stress is calculated as 134 MPa, occupying 48% of the ultimate fracture stress (277 MPa). From then on, because of the increasing obstruction of -45 , 0 and 45 layers, transverse cracks continue to expand steadily until the ultimate fracture of the specimens. Fig.2a presents the side-section image of the laminate corresponding to point A in Fig.1, indicating that the delamination at $90/90$ and $-45/90$ interfaces occurs. Therefore, Figs.1 and 2a demonstrates that the CNT BP layers are sensitive to the delamination in this quasi-isotropic laminate. The final fractured side-section of this laminate shown in Fig.2b,

which corresponds to the point B in Fig.1, further proves the delamination at 90/90 and -45/90 interfaces are the main factors which lead the laminate to failure.

Figure 1: Stress-strain and resistance-strain curve of the studied glass/epoxy laminate

Figure 2: Fractured side-section of the glass/epoxy laminate corresponding to point A (a) and point B (b) in Fig.1

Fig.3a gives the stress-strain and resistance variation-strain curve from the beginning of the loading to the delamination of the carbon fiber/epoxy laminate. It can be clearly seen from Fig.3a that when the first visible high rise in $\Delta R/R_0\%$ appears, raised by 33%, a small load drop simultaneously occurs. This corresponds to the initiation of delamination. Before the delamination initiation, the relation of stress and strain is approximately linear. The observed load drop accompanied by a sudden rise in $\Delta R/R_0\%$ means the delamination initiation, with a stress level of 445 MPa. As shown in Fig.3b, the delamination initiation also actually proceeds at the 90°/90° and -45°/90° interfaces of the laminate. It also shows that the initial delamination of the CNT BP reinforced laminate mainly locates between the CNT BP layers and the prepreg layers, namely the delamination in this case mainly occurs and propagates

along the margin of the CNT BP layers instead of propagating within the CNT BP layers due to the strengthened CNT BP/resin region.

Figure 3: Stress-strain and resistance-strain curve (a) and the fractured side-section (b) at the initiation of delamination for the carbon fiber/epoxy laminate.

Figure 4: Full loading of the carbon fiber/epoxy laminate, (a) stress and resistance variation versus strain and (b) the final fractured side-section

Typical full stress and resistance variation vs strain curve is given in Fig.4a. The stress-strain behaviours and $\Delta R/R_0\%$ also clearly show the initiation of delamination and following progressive damage. This phenomenon suggests that the CNT BPs can be used as an in situ sensor to monitor the onset and propagation of delamination damage without the help of an external detector. The yielded average ultimate strength of the laminate is calculated as 730 MPa. So, the delamination stress, 445 MPa, occupies 61% of the ultimate stress. Fractured side-edge view of the specimens after the full tension is presented in Fig.4b. The middle interface of the laminate almost delaminates completely after the failure. The delamination crack propagates in zig-zag paths (shown in Fig.4b).

Kim et al [16, 17] have reported that $[0/45/-45/90]_s$ laminate tends to delaminate at $90^\circ/90^\circ$ or $-45^\circ/90^\circ$ interfaces under in-plane tensile loading. The experimental carried out in this study also proves the existence of the delamination in this kind of lay-up structure. It is worthy of noting that the measured resistance variation in glass/epoxy laminate is the in-plane resistance, because the glass/epoxy prepreg layers are insulative. Therefore, the BPs in the laminate form parallel circuit in the in-plane direction shown in Fig.5a. Contrarily, the carbon fiber/epoxy prepreg layers are conductive, and the laminate can form conductive path through its thickness. Thus, the conductive carbon fiber layers and BPs form series circuit through the thickness, as shown in Fig.5b.

Figure 5: Conductive paths formed in the laminates, (a) parallel circuit in glass/epoxy laminate, and (b) series circuit in carbon fiber/epoxy laminate

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, conductive CNT BPs were used to in situ monitor the initiation and growth of delamination in $[45/0/-45/90]_s$ laminates. Firstly, the used CNT BPs form uniform CNTs/epoxy interlayers, and the interlayers are bonded well with adjacent glass fiber layers. CNTs within the interlayers are also bonded well with epoxy resin. The uniformly distributed CNTs form three-dimensional conductive paths within interlayers. As expected, CNT BPs are sensitive to the initiation and growth of delamination, showing a sudden rise in the slope of the $\Delta R/R_0\%$ -strain curve for the glass/epoxy laminate, and a jump in $\Delta R/R_0\%$ values for the carbon fiber/epoxy laminate. The potential sensing ability of the BPs used for monitoring the onset of delamination was explored. The results preliminarily prove the potential feasibility of the CNT BP used as structural and functional constituent.

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